

THE PROBLEM OF IMPROVING THE CULTURE OF READING IN THE MODERN STUDENT ENVIRONMENT

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Annotation: The article is devoted to one of the pressing problems – the problem of reading among students and young people. The reasons for the decrease in their interest in reading are studied; the role of understanding and interpreting the text in improving the culture of reading is emphasized.

Keywords: the entertainment industry, the problem of reading, human cultural experience, co-creation, understanding and interpretation of the text.

In recent years, there have been significant changes in attitudes towards reading and its role in society. The entertainment industry, including video games, movies, TV series and social media, has become a powerful alternative to reading. The problem of reading among students and young people is one of the urgent problems of our time. Young people are gradually switching to clip perception of information. This means that short messages, hyperlinks, clicks replace thoughtful reading of works. The rejection of such traditional reading is dangerous because a person gradually stops thinking about what he has read, which leads to a decrease in the quality and level of reading. Reading a paper book not only develops a person's imagination, but also contributes to the brain's function of accumulating knowledge.

According to A.V.Vorontsov, people who read differ from non-readers in that:

- 1) they are able to think in terms of problems, grasp the essence and identify contradictory interrelations of phenomena; assess the situation more adequately and find the right solutions faster;
- 2) have a great memory and an active creative imagination;
- 3) they have a better command of speech: it is more expressive, stricter in understanding and using the dictionary;
- 4) formulate and write more freely;
- 5) it is easier to establish contact with them and it is pleasant to communicate;
- 6) they need independence and inner freedom more, are more critical, independent in their judgments and behavior[4].

Here we are no longer talking about reading and education, but about intelligence, not about knowledge, but about types of thinking, which is especially relevant today.

It was found that a person's cultural experience affects not only his language, but also the conceptual sphere [6].

The ability to read is defined by experts as a reading skill, in the process of mastering which a person goes through four stages: at the first stage, a person learns to translate letters into English and read them; at the second level, he learns to read aloud; at the third, to read to himself; at the fourth, to critically comprehend what he has read. To become a full-fledged, literate reader, it is necessary to master all four levels of reading skills[4].

It was found that a full-fledged perception of a work of art does not exist without a certain reader's culture. Reading culture is an achievement of a personality, the level of reading development, quantitative and qualitative indicators of consciousness, activity and communication are both a product and a factor in personality development. The culture of reading includes: the rational organization of the reading process, depending on the text, the broad context of reading and the properties of the reader; deep, accurate, distinct and complete understanding and "assignment" of text content, accompanied by emotional empathy, critical analysis and creative interpretation of the read; search, analysis and selection of text (books, electronic documents, databases, Internet search engines, etc.) for reading in accordance with the reader's interests and capabilities, as well as the purpose of reading; choice of methods (oral, written) and linguistic means of saving what you read your native and foreign languages (statement, judgment, report, plan, theses, synopsis, abstract, abstract, etc.); The reader's reading culture is realized in the reader's actions as a manifestation of his empathy, co-thinking, co-creation with other people in society, taking into account the laws of nature and society as a whole.

The culture of a qualified reader is "slow reading", which requires a variety of analytical and synthesizing work of the mind and at the same time the work of the senses, a serious emotional "connection". Such reading in the 20s of the XX century was called "feeling". The culture of reading involves intensive spiritual work, which, in fact, consists in creating meanings. Thus, the construction and expression of personal meanings inherent in the very nature of semantic reading is an important feature of the reader's culture. The culture of reading is not formed by itself, but develops in the process of educating a person. An important condition for the development of a reading culture is the inclusion of a personal component (needs, motives, values, meanings) in the structure of educational activities.

Reading is a modern tool for the formation of personality and culture, which contributes to the intellectual and emotional development of a person, his professional and sustainable success. In the context of the rapid development of technology and the information environment, reading remains the most important means of obtaining knowledge and spreading culture, playing a key role in the development of society.

Modern media culture and Internet technologies have significantly changed reading as a cultural practice, especially among young people. Reading is increasingly becoming either a means of obtaining the necessary information or entertainment, which reduces its role as a tool for deep intellectual and aesthetic development. It is important to take these changes into account and find ways to maintain interest in reading complex and meaningful texts in modern conditions.

Thus, depending on the purpose and motives for which people turn to reading, we can focus on two parallel paradigms.

1. Reading as functional literacy - information consumption. Such reading skills are necessary primarily for working with scientific literature, for expanding knowledge and developing logic. Such reading should be inspiring.

2. Reading is a spiritual process of formation of personal characteristics of consciousness, independent creation of mental images, life values under the influence of fiction. Such Reading should be Creative.

G.G.Granik, S.M.Bondarenko, L.A.Kontsevaya adhere to the point of view that to understand the meaning of a text means to highlight the main thing in it.[5]. Therefore, the appropriate orientation of the reader to these research activities in the text and the appropriate technology of this search.

Other scientists consider reading to be a creative process, as a result of which the reader has his own thoughts and experiences, associations are born and imagination develops. According to I.I. Tikhomirova, reading is a creative process[8].

According to the point of view of I.I. Tikhomirova, "the meaning of creative perception is a path leading through the figurative system of a work of art to the soul of a child, it is the expansion of his life experience due to the experience and destinies of literary characters, it is the development of creative abilities." abilities are an immersion into the inner world of people and their relationships. Individually, it is a creative self-realization of the reader's personality, stimulating the need to communicate with the book" [8].

According to the scientist, this is "a way to solve the problem of encouraging reading among young people"[8]. Socially, it is an intellectual and spiritual resource of the nation on the path to culture and progress.

The task of a university teacher is to form the skill of creative reading, to instill a culture of reading, to educate an interested reader who loves reading and a book. A university lecturer teaching humanities has the opportunity to introduce students to reading and re-reading their favorite authors, favorite works of art. You need to read books with pleasure, getting aesthetic pleasure from what you read, only then the rich inner world of the writer opens up to the reader, his thoughts and ideas become clearer.

A person who understands reading needs patience, habit and understanding. "You need to be able to determine the structure of the book, find keywords, build a chain of logical reasoning, following the author...Real reading requires intensive work. As a rule, real reading requires effort and slowness." [1]

Reading is the only intellectual technology for mastering the accumulated knowledge of mankind, and it is quite obvious that the basis of the information culture of society should be precisely the culture of reading, the foundations of which are laid in the family, in the library and educational institutions. The level of intelligence of a nation, the stability of its development and prosperity, as well as the competitiveness of the country directly determine the level and quality of the reading of the younger generation in society.

The main tasks to improve the quality of reading among students are to instill a reading culture, foster interest in reading (primarily classical literature), and develop a reading and information culture. This provides a solution to the main life problems of young people: education, mastery of professional activities, self-education, formation of ideological and moral foundations of personality.

Understanding and interpreting the text requires special attention. Traditionally, both in educational and in fiction, the understanding of the text is subordinated to the disclosure of the

meaning that the author of the work puts in; the relationship of social, economic, moral and cultural changes in the life of society is practically not affected. The innovative approach consists in giving additional meaning, expanding the author's horizons, which is associated with new concepts and paradigms in science, technology, technology, changing criteria of cognition, values and moral attitudes.

Philologist M.M. Bakhtin argues that understanding a text is always a creative act, which includes not only the perception of the author's idea, but also its active rethinking. In the process of reading, the reader becomes a co-author, giving new meanings to the text, creatively comprehending and enriching it.

Thus, knowledge of the culture of reading presupposes the preparation of a psychologically adequate, purposeful, self-developing personality, a specialist in demand in the labor market.

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